

Knowledge and Use of Computer-Assisted Translation Tools on Professional Translation in Nigeria

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Abstract

In recent years, translation as a global industry has witnessed significant changes due to technological advancement that has introduced different tools to facilitate the work of translators. In Nigeria, such changes presuppose that the average Nigerian translator is expected to change with the times. Yet some of these translators do not seem to have sufficient knowledge of such recently developed translation tools as translation memory software, Voice Recognition and Term-base creation tools. Our study sets out to analyse the awareness level of Nigerian translators vis-à-vis state-of-the-art translation tools on the exercise of the profession in Nigeria so as to sensitize them to the need to embrace the new translation tools. This study, anchored on Mary Ellen Kondrat's (1999) theory of professional self-awareness, applies the inductive research method by using questionnaires to collect data from 80 translators on their knowledge and use of new translation tools; on the reason(s) why they may not use the tools; on assumptions about translation-memory tools; and on their views regarding the advantages and disadvantages of the recent tools. Using the quantitative and qualitative methods, the study makes a careful analysis of the questionnaire administered to the sample population and discovers that while there is a low level of use of translation tools (30%) and most recent technologies (translation memory-20%; term management-10%) by translators in Nigeria, there is a high level of use (100%) of hard copy and electronic dictionaries, pen and paper and Microsoft Word by the same translators.

Keywords: Computer-Assisted Translation, Machine Translation, Self-Awareness, Term-base, Translation-memory

Introduction

Over time, translation in Nigeria, like elsewhere around the world, has evolved and entered a new phase with recent technological developments. This situation has made some translators based in Nigeria to migrate from using paper, pen, hard copy dictionaries and glossaries to using the recent translation tools. Unfortunately, some of the tools are under-utilised for reasons ranging from translators of indigenous languages not being able to get much work to raise the money for the tools, to not being able to use computer and manipulate the new tools. There is also the lack of dictionaries and glossaries in indigenous languages that seems to slow down translation in those languages, thereby discouraging translators from investing in new translation tools. In any case, a negligible number of

Nigerian translators who work from French to English and vice versa use some of the tools. It should be noted that translation tools are generally intended to facilitate the work of translators. Thus, using the tools will improve on the speed of translators, enable them to satisfy the needs of the ever-growing clients on the international market and eventually increase their income.

The impact of technology on translation in Nigeria will enable translators to accomplish their translation tasks on time since translation memory tools propose translations that would have been done by the translators in a given context. This makes the translators to avoid repetitions and ensure a consistency of terms with the help of term management tools. This maintains the brand of each client. Also, electronic dictionaries and glossaries which are the most common tools used by translators help to reduce the stress of carrying their hard copy equivalents around, since they can all be installed in one computer and carried around easily. With this kind of mobility of recent translation tools, it is possible for translators to receive jobs and complete their translation tasks from any location in the country. Unfortunately, it would appear not many translators based in Nigeria are conversant with the nature and workings of the recent translation tools.

It is based on this that this research work seeks to find out how knowledgeable Nigerian translators are in the use of current available technological tools for their translation jobs.

The study sought the views of practising translators in Nigeria on their knowledge and use of technology on the translation profession. Non-probability or convenience sampling was applied. A non-probability sampling is a statistical method of drawing representative data by selecting people because of their availability or easy access. The advantage of this type of sampling is the availability and promptitude with which data can be gathered. The samples are generally drawn on human convenience accessibility and proximity to the researcher. Consequently, we made a survey of 100 translators (50 male and 50 female) to whom we administered questionnaires. There were 10 translators of the Commission of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), 30 freelance translators working for ECOWAS, 40 freelance translators from the Nigerian Translators and Interpreters on LinkedIn (professional network) as well as 20 other translators, eight of whom are members of the Nigerian Institute of Translators and Interpreters (NITI) and 12 non-members or yet-to-be members of the NITI. But not for limited resources and want of time, this study would have covered a larger population.

The questionnaire sought background information on the number of years the respondents had worked as translators in Nigeria, where they were trained, if they used recent translation tools while translating, and if they were trained on how to use the tools during their training programme at school. Furthermore, the respondents were asked to give the reasons for their non use of recent translation tools and to score the advantages and disadvantages of the tools. The questionnaires for this study were delivered to the respondents by e-mail. This method of delivery also helped to assess the translators' level of computer literacy. The questionnaires were delivered and retrieved between October 2016 and June 2017.

In all, 80 translators properly completed and returned the questionnaire.

In our data analysis, relative, percentage and cumulative percentage frequencies will

be used. Relative frequency is a comparative measure of the proportion of observed values (category or quantitative value) to the total number of responses within a variable. The equation for calculating relative frequency (f/n) is:

Relative frequency = f/n where f is frequency of specific responses, and n is total number of responses.

A small “ n ” is used to represent the size of a sample and a capital “ N ” is used to represent the size of a population.

A percentage frequency (commonly referred to as simple percentage) is the frequency expressed as a percentage value (out of 100) and can be calculated as follows:

$\% f = f/n \times 100$ where f is frequency of responses, and n is total number of responses within the variable.

The cumulative percentage frequency gives the percentage of observations up to the end of a specific value.

Literature Review

In the same way as the knowledge and use of recent translation tools may still be novel and even very limited in Nigeria, so also is the literature on the use of these recent tools very scanty on the Nigerian professional and intellectual scenes. Nevertheless, scholars and researchers of other climes like Hutchins and Somers (1992), Dohler (1997), Doherty (1997), Austermühl (2001), Bowker (2002), Nogueria (2002), Somers (2003), De Lapp et al (2004) and Byrne (2007) have written variously about CAT tools and how they can be used within professional and academic circles.

Unfortunately, most of these writings do not seem to have brought sufficient value and awareness on the use of CAT tools to the average Nigerian translator. To corroborate the evidence of apparent limited awareness on the use of recent translation tools by the average Nigerian translation, Caleb Ebong and Ibrahim Adedeji (2006, p.74) discuss the product of Computer-Assisted Translation and other recent tools in terms of “the inter-lingual representation of an abstract meaning of the source text, capturing only the linguistic information necessary to generate an appropriate target text without undue influence from the original text.”

This description clearly fits the Machine Translation as “computerised systems responsible for the production of translations from one natural language to another” because, in their view, “it captures only the linguistic information necessary to generate an appropriate target text”. Such a product will only be a paraphrase rather than a translation. Even Garba and Adefarasin (2014, p. 2) do not seem to be sure of the difference between Computer-Assisted Translation (CAT) and Machine Translation (MT) which they use interchangeably as if both terms meant the same thing. Their mention of MT softwares like Google, Systran, Reverso and Babel fish as CAT software confirms the concerns of this study.

Perhaps it was this same discovery that drove Victor Aire (2014) to initiate a pedagogic and practical demonstration of how CAT tools function within a professional setting. He summed up his work by underscoring the following points:

- a). Le logiciel de traduction ne peut jamais produire un texte parfait.

b). ...lorsqu'on aura imprimé, de préférence, à double interligne le texte d'arrivée, l'on devra procéder à une édition minutieuse.
c). Je n'ai pas eu besoin de dactylographier les textes originaux avant de les coller sur la page du logiciel. Je les ai simplement numérisés à l'aide du scanner HP Scanjet G2710, qui produit des textes pouvant être corrigés... (2014, p. 8).

In as much as all these studies discuss and demonstrate the use of CAT tools, none has sought to quantify the degree of lack of awareness in relation to the use of CAT tools by most Nigeria-based translators so as to bring same to the fore in order to ginger such translators to upgrade, add technological value to themselves with a view to satisfying today's translation market demands.

That is what this study seeks to achieve.

Theoretical Framework

Our study will be hinged on the theory of professional self-awareness which is a widely considered concept in psychology and in the practice of social work. Conceived by Mary Ellen Kondrat (1999, p. 452) as an alternate prescription for self-awareness, it relies implicitly on varying definitions of what it means to be a "self" and what it means to be "aware" in a professional setting. The three approaches to professional self-awareness conventionally adopted in the literature include: (a) simple-conscious awareness which describes an awareness of whatever is being experienced; (b) reflective awareness which explains awareness of a self who is experiencing something; and (c) reflexive awareness which explains the self's awareness of how his or her awareness is constituted in direct experience.

While reflective awareness and reflexive awareness seem to be concerned with discovering the inner self of an individual, simple-conscious awareness is more concerned about the external environment of the individual. That is an individual being aware of his/her present realities, noticing his/her surroundings, and being able to name and/or deal with his/her perceptions, feelings, and nuances of behavior.

For the purpose of this study, we shall limit ourselves to simple-conscious awareness which will explain the circumstances surrounding a translator's knowledge and use (or not) of computer-assisted translation tools in the exercise of his/her profession in Nigeria.

At a very basic level, self-awareness is defined in terms of becoming awake to present realities, noticing one's surroundings, and being able to name and/or deal with one's perceptions, feelings, and nuances of behaviour. The self is aware of and can recognize what it is experiencing. This self is understood as the perceiving subject, the locus for sensations, perceptions, and impressions. Influenced by traditions of gestalt and existentialist theory, the emphasis is on the here-and-now contact with the environment. This contact experience can be described as unselfconscious in the sense that attention and awareness are directed at what is experienced by the self rather than at the self who is experiencing something

inwardly. That is what Jean-Paul Sartre refers to as "unreflected consciousness". It is, therefore, more nearly correct to talk about this kind of awareness in terms of pre-self-awareness. However, in the practice literature, close attention to details of the here-and-now experience is identified as one form of self-awareness—that is, the self being more fully aware.

Simple-conscious awareness is what makes both experience and memory possible. Without it, the practitioner would not be able to make accurate observations or correct assessments. It is a necessary condition for articulating one's perceptions. Applied to our study on the knowledge and use of computer-assisted translation tools on professional translation in Nigeria, the simple-conscious awareness theory will not only explain Nigeria-based translators' present realities in relation to their knowledge and use of recent CAT tools, but also their perceptions, feelings and behaviour vis-à-vis these recent translation tools, because after all, knowing or not knowing about recent CAT tools and using or not using them is purely and simply a matter of the self.

Knowledge and Use of Computer-Assisted Translation in Nigeria

With technological advancement, there are so many state-of-the-art translation tools. Among these tools are word processors (Microsoft Word), translation memory tools (Trados, Wordfast, OmegaT, Fluency, MemoQetc), Term management tools (MultiTerm, tlTerm), voice recognition tools, PDF plugin, electronic communication tools, a directory or www-based translators groups, online dictionaries, termbases and glossaries. These sometimes function side-by-side with the three basic types of translation that is human translation, computer-assisted translation (CAT) and fully automated machine translation (FAMT).

In Nigeria, there are eight easily available translation tools. These are:

1. Terminology management tool
2. Translation memory tool
3. Voice Recognition tool
4. Optical Character Recognition tool
5. Dictionaries (hard copy)
6. Electronic dictionaries and glossaries
7. Microsoft word
8. Pen and Paper

A detailed explanation of the nature and usefulness of the above tools is contained in a questionnaire intended to study the actual place of CAT tools in the working lives of translators based in Nigeria. This is analysed under the following headings:

Place where the translators were trained

Of the 80 respondents, 56, representing 70%, were trained abroad as translators; 16, that is 20%, were trained in Nigeria, and three, that is 10%, did not undergo any formal professional training. This implies that while the majority of the translators were trained abroad, some assumed the role of a translator without undergoing any form of training.

Fig 1: Where Respondents studied

This shows that, like in every other country, some linguists translate without any professional training; some were trained on the job, following personal lectures. The Nigerian Institute of Translators and Interpreters (NITI) is seriously working towards ending this unfortunate practice. It has even sent a bill to the National Assembly intended to regulate the professional translation practice in the country.

Existence of CAT tools such as Translation memory tools, Term-base management software, Voice Recognition tools, Electronic dictionaries and glossaries during the training period of the respondents

CAT tools were already in existence during the training period of 56 of the respondents, representing 70%, while during the training of 24 of the respondents, representing 30%, the CAT tools used now in the translation industry were not in existence. This shows that the use of CAT tools in the Nigerian translation industry is not really a new phenomenon.

Question: During your training as a translator, were such tools as translation memory tools, termbase management software, voice recognition tools, electronic dictionaries and glossaries in existence?

Fig. 2: Existence of recent translation tools during translators' training

It should be recalled that 12 of these respondents, representing 15%, as shown in Figure 2, were trained 30 years ago when some of the CAT tools were not yet available in the market. In fact, Translation Support System (TSS), the first CAT tool, was developed by an American company in the mid-80s. So, it will not be surprising to see that the recent translation tools were not known during the training of about 30% of translators in Nigeria.

School programme for training on CAT tools

When asked whether a course was included in the training programme to enable the translators learn how to use the recent Computer-Aided translation (CAT) tools, 32% of the respondents, representing 40% said yes, while 48 of them, representing 60% said no.

Fig. 3: School programme for training on CAT tools

This implies that even though 56 of the respondents, representing 70% had indicated that CAT tools were in existence during their training, only few, about seven or eight, which is 10% of them were taught how to use the tools in school. This also shows that many translation schools have not included Computer-Aided Translation courses in their programmes. If this trend continues, many translators in Nigeria will not be able to use the tools or know their importance in this ever changing world of technology.

Use of CAT tools in translation

From our analysis of respondents' answers, only 24, representing 30% of translators in Nigeria use CAT tools when translating while 70% do not use the tools during the translation process. Even though 40% of the respondents were taught how to use CAT tools, only 30% ended up using them to do their work. This implies that Computer-Aided tools are being neglected in Nigeria.

Translation Tools used in Nigeria

The most common tools used by translators in Nigeria are electronic dictionaries and glossaries (used by 100% of the respondents) and word processors such as Microsoft Word (used by 100% of the respondents). Others are hard copy dictionaries (used by 60% of the respondents) and electronic dictionaries and glossaries (used by 100% of the

respondents). Table 1 below shows that only 20% of the respondents use translation memory tools and the terminology management tool is used by only 10% of the respondents.

Translation Tool	% using it
Terminology management tool.....	10%
Translation memory tool.....	20%
Voice Recognition tool.....	0%
Optical Character Recognition tool.....	0%
Dictionaries (hard copy).....	60%
Electronic dictionaries and glossaries.....	100%
Microsoft word.....	100%
Pen and Paper.....	60%

Table 1: Translation tools used in Nigeria

Table 1 further indicates that none of the respondents uses voice recognition tool and optical character recognition tool. This shows that the most recent translation tools (term management tool, translation memory tool, voice recognition and optical character recognition) are not yet widely used in Nigeria.

Translation memory tools as machine translation and their usefulness

From the above table, it can be said that half (50%) of the translators in Nigeria consider translation memory tools as machine translation. 30% consider the statement as false while 20% do not see translation memory tools as machine translation. This misconception has thrived in the translation industry of Nigeria and it hinders translators from acquiring the recent translation tools since they consider the tools as not useful. It should be noted that while machine translation is a translation done automatically by a machine without the aid of a human translator, translation memory tool is one of the Computer-Aided translation tools available in the market to facilitate the translation process. Translation work is not done by the translation memory tool; rather it is the translator that does the work and s/he is aided by a tool.

Speed of translation memory and term management tools

From our analysis above, only 30% of the respondents use CAT tools while translating. Therefore, this 30% of translators were asked if the tools helped them to finish their work on time or not. 25% of them said yes, while 5% said that the use of such CAT tools as translation memory, term management and voice recognition tools made no difference in terms of speed.

Usefulness of Translation Memory, Term Management and Voice Recognition Tools

Even though only 30% of the respondents use translation memory, term management and voice recognition tools, 2.5% of them consider the tools as not useful to them. However, the majority (27.5%) of those that use the tools consider them valuable.

Fig. 4: Usefulness of Translation Memory, Term Management and Voice Recognition Tools

Of the 30% respondents that use the above mentioned CAT tools, 20% agree that there is consistency of terms when they use the tools, 5% say that they obtained wrong translations if they use the tools while 5% say that there is no difference in using the tools.

Cost of Tools

Of the 30% respondents that use translation memory and terminology management tools, 15% consider the tools to be very expensive, 8% say the tools are worth the cost while 5% consider the tools not expensive. It should be noted that the cost of these tools vary from €400 Euros per license (for Wordfast) through €60 (for memoQ translator pro) to €695 (for Trados freelance). This shows that these tools are expensive and buying them depends on the income of translators.

Fig.5: The Cost of CAT Tools

Time involved in learning how to use Tools

All the 30% of the respondents that use CAT tool such as translation memory and terminology management tools indicated that the time involved in learning how to use these tools is very long.

Fig. 6: Time involved in learning how to use CAT Tools

Reasons for not using Translation Memory, Terminology Management and Voice Recognition Tools

30% of the respondents use the above mentioned tools. Out of the 70% respondents that do not use the tools, all (70%) said their reason was the high cost of the tools. 62% said that the time involved in learning how to use the tools was long. 50% still maintained that the tools were like machine translation tools while 48% said the tools were not useful. Only 5% indicated that the tools were available on the market. This implies that 65% of the respondents that do not use the tools, see the tools on the market but do not recognize them or are unwilling to use them due to other reasons.

Assessing the impact of technology on translation in Nigeria

When asked to assess the impact of technology on translation in Nigeria, 45% of the respondents indicated that the impact was discouraging while 40% indicated that it was fair. 10% rated it satisfactorily while only 5% rated it excellent. This implies that the recent translation tools have not made great impact on the translation industry in Nigeria.

	Percentage Frequency	Cumulative Frequency	Percentage Frequency
Fair	32	40%	40%
Satisfactory	8	10%	50%
Excellent	4	5%	55%
Discouraging	36	45%	100%
Total	80	100%	

Chart 1: Assessing the impact of technology on translation in Nigeria

Assessing Translators' Output since the Advent of Translation Tools

When the respondents were asked to evaluate their output since the advent of Computer-Aided Translation (CAT) tools such as electronic dictionaries, translation memory tools, etc, 60% indicated that their output had been impressive while 30% and 10% indicated that their output had been fair and satisfactory, respectively. None (0%) of the respondents indicated that his/her output had been poor since the advent of the tools. This implies that the advantages of the recent translation tools are more than their disadvantages.

	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency
Fair	32	40%	40%
Satisfactory	8	10%	50%
Excellent	4	5%	55%
Discouraging	36	45%	100%
Total	80	100%	

Chart 2: Assessment of Translators' output since the Advent of Translation Tools

State of Translation in Nigeria

When asked to assess the translation profession in Nigeria, 70% of the respondents indicated that the industry was not organized while 30% indicated that it was organized. Regarding the remuneration for the services of translators in the country, 50% of the respondents considered the job not well paid, while 50% considered their job well paid. Furthermore, 50% indicated that CAT tools were not accessible in Nigeria while 30% maintained that the tools were accessible. As regards the professional body, the Nigerian Institute of Translators and Interpreters (NITI), 60% considered it functional, while 40% considered it not functional. Lastly, 50% of the respondents indicated that the services of

translators were in low demand while 40% indicated that the services are in high demand. Following this, if the services of translators were in low demand, it is likely that the translators will not have enough income to purchase the recent translation tools.

Other Challenges faced by translators in Nigeria

When asked to comment on other challenges faced by translators in Nigeria, many respondents mentioned the lack of professionalism as a threat to the Nigerian translation industry. The industry, according to the respondents, is filled with people who do not have any translation training. Another challenge is lack of jobs for freelance translators in the country, due partly to poor internet connection and the problem of not using translation memory and terminology management tools which international clients demand for the translation of their documents.

Conclusion

This study set out to analyse the awareness level of Nigerian translators in relation to state-of-the-art translation tools in the exercise of the profession in country. This is with a view to sensitising them to the need to embrace the new translation tools. Anchored on Mary Ellen Kondrat's (1999) theory of professional self-awareness, the study applied the inductive research method by using questionnaires to collect data from 80 translators on their knowledge and use of new translation tools. It was discovered that Translation memory, Voice Recognition, Terminology management software were being under-utilised by translators in Nigeria and had not made a great impact on translation in the country. Furthermore, it found out that translators in Nigeria were discouraged from using translation tools not only because of their expensive nature, but also because of the time involved in learning how to use them and the misconception surrounding the tools.

With respect to knowledge of the tools, 50% of the respondents/translators were of the opinion that Translation Memory tools were automatic machine translation which might not be useful to translators. This misconception prevented the respondents from using the tools. Again, 70% of the respondents who do not use CAT tools indicated that the main reason why they did not use the tools was their expensive nature; 62% of the 70% respondents who do not use the tools indicated that their reason for not using them was because of the long period involved in learning how to use them.

Our analysis revealed that 20% of the 30% respondents who use CAT tools indicated that there was consistency of terms when those tools were used. 25% indicated that they finished their work on time when they used the tools, while 27.5% indicated that the tools were useful. With regard to translators' output, 60% of the respondents indicated that their outputs were impressive since they started using translation tools.

On the whole, it should be underscored that though the recent translation tools are not yet being used extensively in Nigeria, they are indeed indispensable to the job of translating. In this vein, this study recommends that translators in Nigeria should be encouraged to acquire and learn how to use these recent technologies because they are generally widely demanded by clients, especially international organisations.

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